

How to view Galileo transformation and Lorentz transformation from a higher level

HuangShan

(Wuhu Institute of Technology, China, Wuhu, 241003)

Abstract: The Galilean transformation and the Lorentz transformation can both be seen as incomplete expressions under a certain equation.

Key words: Galileo transformation, Lorentz transformation, inertia.

$$\text{Galilean transformation: } \begin{cases} (x') = (x - vt) \\ (t') = (t) \end{cases}.$$

$$\text{Lorentz transformation: } \begin{cases} (x') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}}(x - vt) \\ (t') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}}\left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases}.$$

$$\text{And the connection between them is: } \begin{cases} x' = x - vt \\ t' = t \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (x' - vt) = (x - vt) \\ \left(t' + \frac{vt'}{x'}\right) = \left(t + \frac{vt'}{x'}\right) \end{cases},$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (x' - vt) = (x - vt) \\ \left(t' + \frac{vt'}{x'}\right) = \left(t - \frac{vt'}{ic}\right) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \left(x' - \frac{vix'}{c}\right) = (x - vt) \\ \left(t' + \frac{vt'}{x'}\right) = \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases},$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \left(x' - \frac{vix'}{c}\right) = (x - vt) \\ \left(t' - \frac{vt'}{ic}\right) = \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} \left(x' - \frac{vix'}{c}\right)^2 = (x - vt)^2 \\ \left(t' - \frac{vt'}{ic}\right)^2 = \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right)^2 \end{cases},$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (x')^2 + \left(\frac{vix'}{c}\right)^2 - 2\frac{vi(x')^2}{c} = (x - vt)^2 \\ (t')^2 + \left(\frac{vt'}{ic}\right)^2 - 2\frac{v(t')^2}{ic} = \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right)^2 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (x')^2 - \left(\frac{vx'}{c}\right)^2 = (x - vt)^2 \\ (t')^2 - \left(\frac{vt'}{c}\right)^2 = \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right)^2 \end{cases},$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (x')^2 \left[1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2\right] = (x - vt)^2 \\ (t')^2 \left[1 - \left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2\right] = \left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right)^2 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} (x') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}}(x - vt) \\ (t') = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-\left(\frac{v}{c}\right)^2}}\left(t - \frac{v}{c^2}x\right) \end{cases}.$$

Reference : none.